

Safety and Efficacy of a Direct Aspiration First-Pass Technique (Adapt) for Acute Ischemic Stroke: A Retrospective Single Centre Study in South Asian Population

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Abstract:-

Introduction: Acute ischemic stroke (AIS) is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, partly attributable to thromboembolic occlusion of large intracranial arteries.

Purpose: To evaluate the safety and efficacy of ADAPT (a direct aspiration first pass technique) in clot retrieval in patients with acute non-hemorrhagic ischemic stroke.

Methods and materials: Prospectively maintained stroke database was screened for all patients who underwent the ADAPT technique between June 2016 and June 2018. Thirty-five patients were selected who were treated with ADAPT and met inclusion criteria.

Results: The included 35 subjects had a mean age of 53.89 ± 11.31 . The mean NIHSS score was 18.38 ± 7.14 . Thirty-four (97.14%) participants underwent ADAPT and 1(2.86%) participant underwent carotid balloon angioplasty plus ADAPT. Modified Rankin Score (mRS) was achieved ≤ 2 at discharge in 26 participants (74.3%) out of 35 and at 90 days, 25(76.6%) out of 34 participants (one patient died at the time of discharge). TICI (Thrombolysis in Cerebral Infarction) 3 recanalization was seen in 18 (56.25%) patients.

Conclusion: The results of the present study suggest that ADAPT is a feasible technique of mechanical thrombectomy with faster revascularization.

Keywords: Acute ischemic stroke, Thrombectomy, Large vessel occlusion, ADAPT.

I. INTRODUCTION

Acute ischemic stroke is a leading cause of death worldwide.¹ The common causes include thromboembolic occlusion or atherosclerotic stenosis of large intracranial vessels leading to perfusion failure. The lifetime risk of stroke after 55 years of age is 1 in 5 for women and 1 in 6 for men² in India.

The goal of treating AIS is to restore blood flow to ischemic areas at the earliest. Only about 3%–10% of patients with AIS are treated with IVT as they are either out-of-treatment window or IVT is contraindicated.³ Given the

limitations of IVT, MT (mechanical thrombectomy) is a definitive strategy with a wider treatment window and high rates of successful recanalization.

The benefit of MT in acute ischemic stroke due to large vessel occlusion (LVO) has been strongly validated in several landmark multicentre, prospective, randomized, and blinded trials, like Mr. CLEAN, ESCAPE, EXTEND IA, SWIFT PRIME, and REVASCAT.⁴ Few studies are reporting the safety and efficacy of aspiration thrombectomy in South Asian population⁵⁻⁸.

With the development of new wide bore suction catheters, the ADAPT procedure has gained acceptance since it is technically less challenging, has a shorter procedure time, and has good recanalization rates and clinical outcomes. These flexible suction catheters can easily access the twisted and tortuous intracranial arteries and can be used as a primary modality for thrombus retrieval with technical success comparable to stent retrievers.⁴

In recent studies⁹, ADAPT has been found to have the same effectiveness as stent retrievers. Suction thrombectomy works better if the outer diameter of the suction catheter matches the diameter of the occluded vessel. The South Asian population tends to have smaller vessels as compared to the western population. Hence, they represent a population where ADAPT may be better suited as the first-choice technique for MT. To our knowledge, there are no large studies examining the role of ADAPT as a technique of MT in the South Asian population. Therefore, we conducted this study to evaluate the safety and efficacy of ADAPT by assessing procedural and functional outcomes in patients of acute ischemic stroke in a tertiary care center.

II. AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

This study aimed to evaluate the safety and efficacy of ADAPT in clot retrieval in patients with acute ischemic stroke secondary to intracranial large vessel occlusion in terms of revascularization efficacy, duration of the procedure, intra- and post-procedural complications, and clinical recovery at discharge and at 90-day follow up.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a retrospective observational study of a prospectively maintained stroke database conducted in a 750 bedded tertiary care hospital in South India from June 2016 to June 2020 after obtaining permission from the hospital ethical committee.

A. Inclusion Criteria:

- Age \geq 18 years
- ASPECTS (Alberta stroke programme early CT score) score of \geq 6 at baseline CT and DWI ASPECTS \geq 5
- Baseline National institute of health stroke scale (NIHSS) score \geq 6.
- LVO in the anterior or posterior circulation
- A time window of $<$ 6 hrs for anterior circulation and 24 hrs for posterior circulation occlusion.
- No intracerebral hemorrhage at baseline CT

B. Exclusion Criteria:

- NIHSS $<$ 6.
- Age $>$ 80 years
- Subjects with uncontrolled coagulopathy
- Vessels that are too tortuous for access using the penumbra system
- Patients with CNS lesions like brain abscesses, tumors, and aneurysms.

C. Sample size:

Thirty-five subjects who underwent ADAPT as the first pass technique were identified.

D. Data collection:

A prospectively acquired stroke database was screened for all patients who underwent the ADAPT technique for LVO in the anterior and posterior circulation.

All eligible subjects received IVT and were shifted for MRI. Subjects with LVO and a small infarct core on DWI as calculated by the DWI ASPECTS score $>$ 5 were selected for MT.

All angiographic images were evaluated after the procedure and the Thrombolysis in Cerebral Infarction (TICI) score was assigned for assessment of recanalization of the target vessel.

NIH stroke scale at admission and discharge and mRS score at discharge and after 90 days of follow-up were collected. A good clinical outcome was defined as an mRS score \leq 2 at 90 days follow-up. Mortality was defined as death occurring within 90 days of initial presentation. Intra and post-procedural complications including symptomatic and asymptomatic intracranial hemorrhage were recorded.

E. Procedure:

Local anesthesia was preferred for the mechanical thrombectomy. General anesthesia was used in grossly uncooperative patients. Femoral access was preferred, unless radial/ brachial access was needed for anatomical reasons. Two thousand international units of Heparin were administered after the groin access. An 8F short sheath was used to secure the access. 6F Neuron Max (Penumbra, USA) guiding sheath was placed in the cervical internal carotid artery. Triaxial system of ACE 68 (Penumbra, USA), XT 27 (Stryker, USA), and a suitable 0.014" guidewire was navigated to the site of occlusion and the suction catheter (ACE 68) was connected to the Penumbra aspiration pump for the suction thrombectomy. Adjuvant techniques (stent retriever and/ or intra-arterial tirofiban) were used when needed to achieve successful reperfusion.

Few cases of ADAPT technique mentioned below:

IV. FIGURES

A. Case 1)

CT scan of the same patient (Image A) shows left hyperdense MCA and MRI shows (Image B&C) diffusion restriction in right MCA territory with blooming in MCA in

SWI in (image D) s/o thrombosis. MR Angiogram (image E&F) of the same patient shows absent flow-related signals in the petrous segment right ICA and right MCA.

Fig. 1 (A,B,C,D,E,F,G,H): 57 years old male who came with a complaint of left-sided weakness for 4 hours.

The same patient underwent ADAPT, Pre-procedural DSA (image G) shows right ICA occlusion at the petrous

segment, and post-procedural DSA (image H) shows complete distal filling of right ACA and MCA.

B. Case 2)

Fig. 2: 57-year male came with a complaint of left-sided weakness for 4 hours.

CT scan of the same patient (image A) shows hyperdense M2 segment of the right MCA and subsequent MRI shows diffusion restriction (image B&C) in right corona radiata, angiogram (image D&E) shows absent flow related signals in the right ICA and MCA. The same patient

underwent ADAPT, Pre-procedural DSA (image F) shows right ICA and MCA occlusion from the origin, and post-procedural DSA (image H) shows complete filling of right ICA and MCA.

C. Case 3)

Fig. 3: 57 years old male came with giddiness for 3 hours 30 min

CT scan of same patient shows hyperdense right vertebral and proximal basilar artery (image A&B) and MRI shows an acute infarct in the right cerebellum (image C&D) and right half of the midbrain (not shown here). Pre-

procedural DSA shows occlusion of the right vertebral artery occlusion (image E) and post procedural DSA shows distal filling of right vertebral and basilar artery (image F).

D. Case 4)

Fig. 4: 57 years old female came with complaint of right side weakness.

MRI shows an acute infarct in left capsuloganglionic region (images A&B) and absent flow related signal in left M2 MCA and distal to it in MR angiogram (Image C). Pre-procedural DSA shows occlusion of left MCA and post-procedural DSA shows near complete filling of MCA (TICI 2c).

F. Statistical methods

Descriptive analysis: Descriptive analysis was carried out by mean and standard deviation for quantitative variables, frequency, and proportion for categorical variables.

Categorical outcomes were compared between study groups using Chi-square test using SPSS. P value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant

V. RESULTS

A total of 48 patients were included in the study who underwent ADAPT as an initial mechanical thrombectomy technique. Out of 48, ADAPT failed in thirteen patients in which the stent retriever or a combined technique was used to achieve successful reperfusion so a total of 35 patients were included in the final analysis which has successful revascularization with ADAPT.

The demographic profile of the study is shown in table-1.

The number of attempts to achieve successful revascularization by ADAPT were as follow: single in 21 patients, 2 in 9 patients, 3 in 4 patients, and 4 attempts in one patient.

Table 1: Descriptive analysis of baseline parameters in study population (N=35)

Parameter	Summary
Age in years (mean±SD)	53.89±11.31
Gender	
Male	25(71.43%)
Female	10(28.57%)
NIHSS (mean±SD)	18.38±7.14
Preoperative mRS 0-2	35(100%)
Duration of symptoms (hrs) (mean±SD)	2.51±1.21
Door to image (min) (mean±SD)	12.17±7.26
CT ASPECTS	8.60±2.03
Location of LVO	
Middle cerebral arteries (MCA)	13(37.14%)
Basilar artery	8(22.86%)
Tandem occlusions	6(17.14%)
Internal carotid artery bifurcation	4(11.43%)
Intracranial internal carotid artery	3(8.57%)
Basilar junction occlusion	1(2.86%)
Intravenous rtPA (tissue plasminogen activator)	14(40%)

Pre- and post-intervention TICI grades are summarised in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2: Descriptive analysis of procedural parameters in study population (N=35)

Parameter	Summary
Door to puncture (min)	54.66±24.78
TICI grading pre-intervention	
0	32(91.43%)
1	2(5.71%)
2a	1(2.86%)
Type of mechanical thrombectomy	
ADAPT	34(97.14%)
Carotid balloon angioplasty + ADAPT	1(2.86%)
Puncture to recanalization (PTR)min	33.74±15.47

TICI post intervention	
0	0(0%)
1	0(0%)
2A	3(8.6%)
2B	3(8.6%)
2C	9(25.7%)
3	20(57.1%)
Intra-arterial tPA	1(2.86%)
Use of Gp 2b/3a antagonists	2(5.71%)
Carotid Artery Stenting	2(5.71%)
Endovascular complications	1(2.86%)
Post-procedure Bleeding	8(22.86)
MRS at discharge	
0 to 2	26(74.3%)
3 to 5	8(22.9%)
6	1(2.9%)
MRS at 90 days	
0 to 2	26(76.6%)
3 to 5	6(17.5%)
6	2(5.9%)

Out of 35, 26(74.3%) patients had an mRS score of 0 to 2 at discharge and the score was the same at 90 days of follow-up. Out of 29 patients who achieved TICI 2b or greater reperfusion after ADAPT, 23 (79 %) achieved an mRS score of 0 to 2 at 90 days.

VI. DISCUSSION

In this retrospective study to evaluate the safety and efficacy of the ADAPT technique in endovascular stroke thrombectomy, 35 patients were included and the majority of them (95%) had favourable reperfusion (TICI 2b and above) with good clinical outcomes (76.6 % with mRS between 0-2 at 3 months).

The median age in our study was 53.89 ± 11.31 years which is younger compared to prior literature such as the PENUMBRA¹⁰ study.

As per the current study, the median NIHSS score was 18.38 ± 7.14 which correlates with the NIHSS score of a few other studies like the MR CLEAN trial¹² and PENUMBRA PIVOTAL¹⁰ trial. The Median CT ASPECTS score in this study was 8.60 ± 2.03 which indicates a lower infarct burden. This might again explain the good outcomes seen in our patients. Appropriate patient selection with a low infarct burden on CT may be an important factor leading to good clinical outcomes. This correlates with findings of previous studies like MR CLEAN¹⁶ study, Benjamin Gory¹³ et al, Pierre De Marini et al¹⁴.

The commonest site of LVO was the M1/ M2 segment of MCA (37%) in our study which correlates with many other studies where the M1 segment of the middle cerebral artery was the commonest site of large vessel occlusion^{12,15,13}

The mean puncture to recanalization time (PTR) in our study was 34 minutes. Recanalization is an important predictor of stroke outcome as timely restoration of regional cerebral perfusion helps salvage threatened ischemic tissue. A systematic review and meta-analysis of 18 studies including 2893 patients by, H.Henkes et al¹⁶ concluded that ADAPT gives statistically shorter groin-to-reperfusion time. The approximate median PTR was ~50 minutes in mechanical thrombectomy using stent retrievers⁶.

TICI grade 2B or greater reperfusion was used as an endpoint to define successful reperfusion¹⁸. Successful reperfusion was achieved in 29 patients (80 %) in the current study. The study results correlate with the trials with smaller sample sizes like A Bose, et al¹⁶ (n=20), and Turk et al¹⁹ (n=37) while the meta-analysis on the ADAPT technique by Benjamin glory¹³ et al (n=1378) documented 69% TICI > 2b reperfusion. Large randomized control trials on stent retrieval have demonstrated a successful recanalization rate of TICI 2B or higher in 75-81%.^{10, 12} Higher rates of successful recanalization in the current study may be attributed to a smaller sample size. In a study by Justus F Kleine et al²⁰ who examine the neurologic outcome of TICI 2B and TICI 3 in subjects with AIS with MCA occlusion treated successfully with MT, they concluded neurologic outcome was substantially better in TICI 3 than TICI 2b. We observed a high chance of good outcome in patients with TICI 2B or greater recanalisation (79%) emphasizing the importance of reperfusion effect on clinical outcomes.

Around a quarter of the patients in the study group had an LVO in the posterior circulation. ADAPT is better suited for occlusions in the basilar trunk due to the relatively straight line of force for the suction effect.

A study by Marie Louise E. Bernsen et al done on Aspiration Versus Stent Retriever Thrombectomy for Posterior Circulation Stroke first-line aspiration is associated with a shorter procedure time, better reperfusion, and better clinical outcome.

The incidence of sICH is less in MT which is 8(25%) in the current study and correlates with BENJAMIN GORY trial¹³. The incidence of sICH in ADAPT and stent retrieval was found to be the same in a systematic review and meta-analysis by STAPLETON CJ et al²¹ and ASTER trial⁶.

mRS has been used to determine the functional outcome of endovascular therapy. mRS score ≤ 2 carries a good functional outcome. The current study showed an mRS score of ≤ 2 at 90 days in 26 patients (76.6%) correlating with R blanc et al¹⁷ (n=80). The finding was in contrast to BENJAMIN GORY trial¹³ on ADAPT technique for acute ischemic stroke in large vessel occlusion showed mRS ≤ 2 in 52% (n=1378). Better functional outcomes in the current

study can be attributed to a higher average CT ASPECTS score suggestive of a small ischemic core.

VII. LIMITATIONS

One major limitation is the retrospective, observational design which is prone to selection biases. Another limitation was small sample size and we didn't compare efficacy of ADAPT with stent retriever first approach or intravenous thrombolysis.

VIII. CONCLUSION

To conclude ADAPT is a feasible technique resulting in fast revascularization times with good clinical outcomes. However, the results need to be verified in large prospective randomized trials to determine the best strategy.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Katan M, Luft A. Global Burden of Stroke. *Seminars in Neurology*. 2018;38(02):208-211. doi:10.1055/s-0038-1649503
- [2.] Das S, Banerjee T. Fifty years of stroke researches in India. *Annals of Indian Academy of Neurology*. 2016;19(1):1. doi:10.4103/0972-2327.168631
- [3.] Geraghty S. Hemorrhagic and Ischemic Stroke: Medical, Imaging, Surgical and Interventional Approaches. *Journal of Vascular and Interventional Radiology*. 2012;23(9):1257. doi:10.1016/j.jvir.2012.05.057
- [4.] Touma L, Filion KB, Sterling LH, Atallah R, Windle SB, Eisenberg MJ. Stent Retrievers for the Treatment of Acute Ischemic Stroke. *JAMA Neurology*. 2016;73(3):275. doi:10.1001/jamaneurol.2015.4441.
- [5.] Zi W, Wang H, Yang D, et al. Clinical Effectiveness and Safety Outcomes of Endovascular Treatment for Acute Anterior Circulation Ischemic Stroke in China. *Cerebrovascular Diseases*. 2017;44(5-6):248-258. doi:10.1159/000478667
- [6.] Li C, Zhao W, Wu C, et al. Outcome of endovascular treatment for acute basilar artery occlusion in the modern era: a single institution experience. *Neuroradiology*. 2018;60(6):651-659. doi:10.1007/s00234-018-2011-7
- [7.] Uno J, Kameda K, Otsuji R, et al. A Direct Aspiration First Pass Technique in Japanese Real-World Clinical Setting. *Operative Neurosurgery*. 2018;17(2):115-122. doi:10.1093/ons/opy349
- [8.] Matsumoto H, Nishiyama H, Tetsuo Y, Takemoto H, Nakao N. Initial clinical experience using the two-stage aspiration technique (TSAT) with proximal flow arrest by a balloon guiding catheter for acute ischemic stroke of the anterior circulation. *Journal of NeuroInterventional Surgery*. 2016;9(12):1160-1165. doi:10.1136/neurintsurg-2016-012787
- [9.] Schramm P, Navia P, Papa R, et al. ADAPT technique with ACE68 and ACE64 reperfusion catheters in ischemic stroke treatment: results from the PROMISE study. *Journal of neurointerventional surgery*. 2019;11(3):226-231. doi:10.1136/neurintsurg-2018-014122

- [10.] The Penumbra Pivotal Stroke Trial. *Stroke*. 2009;40(8):2761-2768. doi:10.1161/strokeaha.108.544957
- [11.] Krasteva MP, Lau KK, Mordasini P, Tsang ACO, Heldner MR. Intracranial Atherosclerotic Stenoses: Pathophysiology, Epidemiology, Risk Factors and Current Therapy Options. *Advances in Therapy*. 2020;37(5):1829-1865. doi:10.1007/s12325-020-01291-4
- [12.] Fransen PS, Beumer D, Berkhemer OA, et al. MR CLEAN, a multicenter randomized clinical trial of endovascular treatment for acute ischemic stroke in the Netherlands: study protocol for a randomized controlled trial. *Trials*. 2014;15(1). doi:10.1186/1745-6215-15-343
- [13.] Gory B, Armoiry X, Sivan-Hoffmann R, et al. A direct aspiration first pass technique for acute stroke therapy: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *European Journal of Neurology*. 2017;25(2):284-292. doi:10.1111/ene.13490
- [14.] De Marini P, Nayak S, Zhu F, et al. A direct aspiration first pass technique with the new ARC catheter for thrombectomy of large vessel occlusion strokes: A multicenter study. *Interventional Neuroradiology*. 2018;25(2):187-193. doi:10.1177/1591019918803962
- [15.] Schramm P, Navia P, Papa R, et al. ADAPT technique with ACE68 and ACE64 reperfusion catheters in ischemic stroke treatment: results from the PROMISE study. *Journal of neurointerventional surgery*. 2019;11(3):226-231. doi:10.1136/neurintsurg-2018-014122
- [16.] Bose A, Henkes H, Alfke K, et al. The Penumbra System: A Mechanical Device for the Treatment of Acute Stroke due to Thromboembolism. *American Journal of Neuroradiology*. 2008;29(7):1409-1413. doi:10.3174/ajnr.a1110.
- [17.] Lapergue B, Blanc R, Gory B, et al. Effect of Endovascular Contact Aspiration vs Stent Retriever on Revascularization in Patients With Acute Ischemic Stroke and Large Vessel Occlusion. *JAMA*. 2017;318(5):443. doi:10.1001/jama.2017.9644
- [18.] Higashida RT, Furlan AJ. Trial Design and Reporting Standards for Intra-Arterial Cerebral Thrombolysis for Acute Ischemic Stroke. *Stroke*. 2003;34(8). doi:10.1161/01.str.0000082721.62796.09
- [19.] Turk AS, Spiotta A, Frei D, et al. Initial clinical experience with the ADAPT technique: A direct aspiration first pass technique for stroke thrombectomy. *Journal of NeuroInterventional Surgery*. 2013;6(3):231-237. doi:10.1136/neurintsurg-2013-010713
- [20.] Kleine JF, Wunderlich S, Zimmer C, Kaesmacher J. Time to redefine success? TIC1 3 versus TIC1 2b recanalization in middle cerebral artery occlusion treated with thrombectomy. *Journal of Neuro Interventional Surgery*. 2016;9(2):117-121. doi:10.1136/neurintsurg-2015-012218.
- [21.] Stapleton CJ, Leslie-Mazwi TM, Torok CM, et al. A direct aspiration first-pass technique vs stentriever thrombectomy in emergent large vessel intracranial occlusions. *Journal of Neurosurgery*. 2018;128(2):567-574. doi:10.3171/2016.11.jns161563.